

2 - part of the experiments.

Prepare similar samples of diesel fuel with water and hydrogels. To determine the effect of temperature on the rate of moisture absorption in diesel fuel, to do

this, prepare a water bath and heat to a temperature of 50°C, 70°C and 80°C, and each time observe the absorption of moisture, and determine the time for complete absorption of moisture in each sample.

Table 2**The influence of temperature on the rate of water absorption**

Test time, sec (min)	50°C	70°C	80°C
Hydrogel concentration y.			
5 g hydrogels	52 sec	39 sec	35 sec
10 g hydrogels	20 sec	17 sec	15 sec
15 g hydrogels	12 sec	10 sec	8 sec

Observations showed that within 10 min. the gel completely absorbed the water.

At the same time, the highest efficiency of the process was noted at a gel concentration of 10 g. and temperature 40-500 C.

References

1. Barkhanadzhyan A.L., Khakimov R.M., Ibragimov B.D., Sobirova D.K., Abdukarimova G.U., & Airapetov D.A. The problem of the use of waste paints and varnishes, and their disposal // Bulletin of the Tomsk Polytechnic University Georesources Engineering. 2020, No. 331(9), pp. 179–185. [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <http://izvestiya.tpu.ru/archive/article/view/2821/>.
2. Barkhanadzhyan A.L., Khakimov R.M., Ibragimov B.D., Tillaev A., Airapetov D.A. Characteristics of paint and varnish materials for road marking based

on local raw materials // Problems of modern science and education. 2022., No. 1 (170) 7-11. [Electronic resource]. Access mode: <https://ipi1.ru/images/PDF/2022/170/PSME-1-170-.pdf>

3. Kuliev A.M. Chemistry and technology of additives to oils and fuels. Moscow. Chemistry, 1972. 358 p.

4. Shadimetov Yu., Ayrapetov D., Botir E. Transport, ecology and health / International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and Technology, 2021. VOLUME 8. ISSUE 4. 33 17226-17230 pp. [Электронный ресурс]. Режим доступа: <http://www.ijarset.com/upload/2021/april/33-botir-28.PDF/>

5. Barkhanadzhyan A.L. Operating materials used in vehicles. Textbook. - T.: "VNESHINVESTPROM" printing 2019 - 230 p.

CORROSION PROTECTION OF HEAT EXCHANGERS USED ON THE DEVICE FOR AMINE CLEANING OF REGENERATION GASES "SHURTAN OIL AND GAS PRODUCTION DEPARTMENT"

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ЗАЩИТА ТЕПЛООБМЕННОГО АППАРАТА ОТ КОРРОЗИИ, ПРИМЕНЯЕМОГО В УСТРОЙСТВЕ ПО ОЧИСТКЕ РЕГЕНЕРАЦИОННЫХ ГАЗОВ С ПОМОЩЬЮ АМИНА «ШУРТАНСКОЕ НЕФТЕГАЗОДОБЫВАЮЩЕЕ УПРАВЛЕНИЕ»

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Abstract

One of the most pressing problems of gas-processing enterprises is the large corrosion of the corpus callosum of the horizontal heat exchanger, which is used in the process of regeneration of the absorbed absorbent (diethanolamine) in the absorption of gas. This article discusses the causes of corrosion on the body of the appliance and how to deal with them.

Аннотация

Одной из актуальных проблем на газоперерабатывающих предприятиях является быстрая коррозия корпуса горизонтального кожухотрубчатого теплообменника, применяемой в процессе регенерации насыщенного абсорбента (диэтанолamina) при абсорбционной очистке природного газа от кислых компонентов. В данной статье рассмотрены причины коррозии корпуса устройства и способы ее устранения.

Keywords: casing tubular heat exchanger, absorbent, diethanolamine, tubular bead, intercellular space.

Ключевое слово: кожух трубчатый теплообменник, абсорбент, диэтаноламин, трубная сборка, межклеточное пространство.

The dynamic development of various branches of the national economy is characterized by the large-scale use of heat exchange plants and an increase in the requirements for them. At the same time, the most pressing problem is the reduction of the overall dimensions and weight of such devices. In addition, in some cases, it is necessary to reduce the temperature difference and wall temperature.

Similar problems are faced by chemical, oil and gas, energy, metallurgical and other industrial enterprises using heat exchangers.

In the oil and gas processing industry, thermal processes such as heating and cooling of liquids and gases, deer condensation are widespread. Such processes are carried out on heat exchange equipment.

A large share of the process equipment used in the oil refining and chemical industries is heat exchange equipment. Thermal equipment used in the chemical industry averages 15-18% of the total equipment, and in the oil and gas processing industry this figure is 50%.[1]

The substances involved in the heat exchange process are called heat carriers. High temperature substances that transfer heat from themselves to the heated medium are called heating agents. Substances having a low temperature compared to the cooled medium and receiving heat from the environment are called cooling agents.

When selecting the agents used to supply or produce heat on heat exchange equipment, the following properties are given importance: 1) the degree of heating or cooling of the necessary medium and the ability to control it; 2) achieving a high heat exchange rate at minimum massive and volumetric flow rates; 3) it is desirable that it is infallible, non-poisonous, heat resistant; 5) heat exchange equipment shall not destroy the prepared material; 6) should not be rare and accessible.

In most cases, it is economically feasible to use heat products, semi-finished products and waste from production as heating agents.

In industry, heat exchange processes are carried out for the purposes of: 1) maintaining the temperature of the process at a given level; 2) heating of cold products or cooling of hot products; 3) deer condensation; 4) laying solutions and so on. [1]

Absorbent regeneration (diethanolamine is used as absorbent in many gas processing plants), saturated with the absorption method of cleaning gases from oxygen components, is carried out at high temperatures (120-130) and low pressure (90-95 kPa). Tubular heat exchange plants are used to regenerate saturated absorbent in gas processing plants when heated from 50-60 to 100-110. During regeneration, the temperature in desorber 120-130 is formed by a low-pressure water deer sharpened in the refrigerating device. Access to the desorber is performed by increasing the temperature of the absorbent saturated in the heat exchange device with a temperature from 50-60 to 110-120, using the

regenerated absorbent exiting the lower part of the desorber as a heating agent. The regenerated absorbent heats the saturated absorbent and cools it itself. When saturated absorbent is heated, saturated absorbent passes through pipeline part of heat exchange structure, and regenerated absorbent passes through outside of pipelines. This is due to the fact that the main element of the heat exchange device is this shell, aggressive medium is always transferred from the inside of the pipeline, since in many cases the pipe, holes and covers are made of the appropriate alloyed metal, that is, the shell, the barrier segment, etc. It is problematic that when regenerating absorbent concentrated in purification devices using amines from gas processing plants, corrosion of the shells of horizontal-clad heat exchange plants used in heating diethanolamine. According to the results of the studies, the hole of the shut-off part of the tubular heat exchanger device used in this process depends on the following factors.[4]

1. The medium of 30% of the concentrated solution of regenerated diethanolamine moving from the shell and the inter-wire space causes corrosion of the shell wall.

2. As a heating agent, partially preserved harmful gases (H_2S , CO_2 , etc.) in the composition of a solution of regenerated amine diethanol transferred from the pipe space of a tubular heat exchange device form a gas layer (gas pad) in the upper part of the device. The affected gas acts high pressure on the shell of the device, causes corrosion of the shell of the device and inlet unions and a hole in the shell.

3. The mechanical particles in the regenerated diethanolamine composition supplied on the device as a heating agent become one of the main causes of influence on the device shoulder and nozzle at the inlet.

- By eliminating the above-mentioned problems, it is possible to improve the long-term reliable and self-contained operation of the tubular heat exchange device used in this process. To do this, you must:

- Prevent the regenerated diethanol used in the device as a heating agent from dropping the amine concentration at a predetermined (30%) cost.

- The shell of heat exchange plants used in the process of amine regeneration at many gas processing plants is made of 09G2S-12 grade steel. steel of the brand is used for manufacture of shell, covering, flange and other parts of devices used in neutral and aggressive media. The regenerated diethalamine used in the heating of diethanolamine, moving from the pipe space of the tubular heat exchange device, creates a business environment. Steel of the grade does not have high corrosion resistance in a busy business environment. For heat exchange devices used in high and medium aggressive media, it is advisable to manufacture shells from X18H10T grades of steel. Steel of the grade is used at high pressure, in conditions of high temperature and medium aggressiveness 600 X18H10T, in the manufacture of shell, bottom, flange, bolt, nut, stud, con-

necting pipes and other parts of mounted chemical devices. The horizontal tubular heat exchange unit with a horizontal pipe used in this process can be replaced by a heat exchange unit with a vertical pipe to prevent the formation of a gas layer in the inter-pipe space.[3]

- Inhibitors can be used to slow corrosion in aggressive environments. With corrosion protection of devices used in the regeneration of acid gas saturated absorbers it is possible to reduce the corrosion rate by using the EC-3005A Nalco/Exxon Energy Chemicals corrosion inhibitor.

By eliminating the above problems, it is possible to ensure long-term and uninterrupted operation of the device.

References

1. Z.Salimov. Neft va gazni qayta ishlash jarayonlari va uskunalari. – T.: «Aloqachi», 2010, 508 bet.
2. Salokhiddinov F.A. State of study of the problem and geological-physical conditions of objects of research // "School of Science" January 2020.
3. Technological regulations of Shurtanneftegaz production department.
4. *A.M.Khurmatov, G.B.Rakhimov*. Calculation of heat transfer and heat transfer in a pipe apparatus in heating gas condensate// «Scientific and technical journal of NamIET» VOL 6 – Issue (1) 2021, ISSN 2181-8622